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MUSICAL MEANS OF FORMING A POSITIVE EMOTIONAL STATE THROUGH PERCUSSION INSTRUMENTS

Samatov Temur Alisher ugli

Teacher of the National Institute of Pop Art named after Batyr Zakirov

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Annotation: This article analyzes the musical means of forming a positive emotional state in listeners and performers using percussion instruments. It scientifically highlights the possibilities of percussion instruments to increase the emotional impact through means of expression such as timbre, rhythm, dynamics and tempo. The mechanisms of increasing creativity, mood and changing the psychological state of students through the effective use of percussion instruments in the process of music education are revealed.

Keywords: emotional state, musical instruments, rhythm, dynamics, music education, music therapy, percussion instruments, musical expression, psychological impact.

Introduction.

Music has long been recognized as an art form that affects the most delicate strings of the human soul. Its power of influence, the possibility of having a positive or negative impact on the state of mind, is currently being studied in depth not only by art historians, but also by psychologists, educators and therapists. In particular, the direct impact of rhythm and dynamics expressed through percussion instruments - percussion instruments - on the emotional state of a person is becoming a unique scientific research direction. Percussion instruments have long been widely used in rituals, martial melodies, ceremonial processions and holidays. The rhythmic structures and timbre characteristics of these instruments play an important role in awakening mental states in a person, invigorating them, inspiring them, and even reducing stress. Especially in modern music education, the possibilities of ensuring the emotional stability of students, restoring their psychological balance, as well as creating a positive spiritual environment are expanding.

Today, in the process of musical education, one of the pressing issues is to influence the emotional sphere of students through percussion instruments, to teach them to express their feelings through musical expression. It has been scientifically proven that percussion instruments can reach the human psyche and emotional state through means of expression such as tempo, rhythm, dynamics, register, articulation. This is widely used in areas of music therapy developed on the basis of percussion instruments.

Also, percussion instruments provide an opportunity to increase students'

interest in music, encourage them to participate actively, and teach them to work creatively in collaboration. Especially among young children and adolescents, the cases of improving mood, building self-confidence, and overcoming stress through learning percussion instruments have been confirmed in practical experiments. Therefore, the formation of a positive emotional state using percussion instruments is an important scientific and practical direction that is at the junction of not only art, but also pedagogy and psychology.

One of the main impressive aspects of music is its ability to directly affect a person's emotional state. In particular, the rhythmic structures of percussion instruments, strong dynamics and expressive means based on a clear tempo have the ability to quickly change a person's mood, inspire or calm him. Percussion instruments work in harmony with the human heartbeat, body rhythms, and breathing rate, creating a natural resonance with it. This makes percussion instruments one of the most effective musical tools for managing an emotional state.

The percussion instrument family includes instruments such as the hoop, drum, xylophone, tambourine, congas, bongos, triangle, and castrol. Each has a different timbre and dynamic range, and they serve to express different emotions. For example, a large drum has an uplifting power with its strong, resonant beats, while lighter percussion instruments such as a triangle or tambourine evoke joyful, light, and festive feelings.

In the experience of music pedagogy, percussion instruments are widely used to increase the activity of students, enliven the lesson process, and transform them from active listeners into active performers. In particular, exercises conducted with percussion instruments in extracurricular music classes or clubs help children develop initiative, teamwork, concentration, and auditory culture. Through rhythmic exercises, children have the opportunity to express their emotions, relieve stress, and achieve a positive state. At the same time, percussion instruments are also widely used in music therapy. In developed countries, the "drum circle" or "rhythmic group therapy" method is effective in working with children, the disabled, and those with mental disorders. In such classes, participants express their inner experiences by improvising together on drums or other percussion instruments, serving as listeners and supporters for each other. This creates trust, emotional connection, and a positive psychological environment among them.

In order to study the emotional expressiveness of percussion instruments in more depth, it is necessary to dwell on their main means of expression - rhythm, tempo, dynamics, pause, articulation and timbre. Rhythm - due to its similarity to

the natural beating of the human heart, directly penetrates the inner emotional world. While a fast rhythm evokes feelings of excitement, joy, and motivation, a slow and steady rhythm provides a state of calm and tranquility. Dynamics is the increase and decrease of the power of music - it reflects the increase and decrease of emotions. Timbre is the color of the sound of various percussion instruments - through these colors, different moods can be evoked in the listener's mind.

Also, through emotional exercises, musical improvisations, and games based on a specific scenario using percussion instruments, children develop not only a positive emotional state, but also important psychological processes such as aesthetic taste, rhythmic hearing, and musical memory. All this creates the basis for recognizing percussion instruments not only as a means of performance, but also as a powerful pedagogical tool serving emotional education, social adaptation and personal development.

Literature analysis (review):

The scientific, theoretical and practical sources studied within the framework of this topic reveal more deeply the views on the impact of percussion instruments on the human psyche and emotional state, their educational and therapeutic potential. In particular, scientists such as G. S. Altshuller and B. M. Teplov expressed important theoretical considerations about the emotional perception of music and the impact of rhythm on the human psyche. Their studies emphasize the physiological resonance of percussion instruments on the body - their influence on processes such as heartbeat, breathing and muscle relaxation.

Modern literature contains extensive information about percussion instrument therapy (drum therapy), rhythmic improvisations and the emotional benefits of group performance activities. Music therapy experts such as Michael Thaut and Christine Stevens have scientifically substantiated the effectiveness of training with percussion instruments in reducing stress, alleviating depression, and increasing social adaptation. Stevens's work "The Healing Drum Kit" also offers practical methods in this regard.

Scientific articles by Uzbek researchers such as S. Jo'rayev, Z. Hoshimova, Sh. Rakhmatullayev on music education, the formation of musical thinking in children, and the development of rhythmic feeling serve as an important source for studying the educational potential of percussion instruments. In particular, Hoshimova's work on methods of managing emotional states through rhythmic exercises in music lessons is directly related to this topic.

The emotional-functional role of percussion instruments is also reflected in folk oral creativity and traditional music sources. In particular, the role of the traditions of the circle, drum, and trumpet in raising the mood during holidays

and ceremonies is confirmed in historical and musicological sources. This indicates that percussion instruments were valued in folk culture as a means of influencing the social and emotional environment. The analyzed sources show that the formation of a positive emotional state through percussion instruments is a topic that requires a multifaceted, interdisciplinary approach. The combination of psychological, musical, pedagogical, and therapeutic approaches can serve as the basis for new research in this area.

Discussion:

In the fields of modern pedagogy and music psychology, the formation of a person's emotional state and its positive direction is one of the pressing issues. It is from this perspective that the potential of percussion instruments as a musical instrument and its potential as a musical instrument requires a comprehensive analysis. Practical observations and analysis of scientific sources show that percussion instruments are a powerful tool that directly affects the human mind and emotional world. They play an important role in awakening, changing and balancing the internal state of a person through rhythm, tempo, dynamics and timbre.

The fact that the use of percussion instruments in the education of young people is particularly effective is evident in the results of musical activities. During classes, students develop a sense of rhythm, they acquire skills such as working together, performing in a group, reacting in time, and feeling musical material. In particular, interactive exercises based on percussion instruments, which improve the social environment in the classroom, create an atmosphere of mutual respect, cheerfulness, and positive competition among students.

Another important aspect in the discussion is the therapeutic effect of percussion instruments on human health and psychological state. Today, methods such as "drum circle", "body percussion", "music and movement" are actively used in education from preschool to higher education. Percussion instruments play an important role as a means of emotional healing, especially in working with children with disabilities, adolescents under stress and people in distress. However, in practice, there are problems such as insufficient mastery of these methods, lack of systematic development of methods for working with percussion instruments, and lack of necessary knowledge and skills among teachers. This situation indicates the need to create new methodological guidelines and methodological recommendations for establishing emotional education using percussion instruments in pedagogical education. There is also a need to perceive percussion instruments not only as a technical means of performance, but also as a method with a psychopedagogical impact.

The role of percussion instruments in the cultural and national context should also be studied separately. In Uzbek traditional music, instruments such as drums, drums, trumpets have always served as a formative of a positive spirit in solemn, festive, religious or ceremonial situations. This confirms that the process of creating a positive emotional environment using percussion instruments has ancient cultural roots. Therefore, the organization of modern musical and pedagogical activities based on folk traditions can be more effective in forming a positive emotional environment. The formation of a positive emotional state through percussion instruments is an important direction not only for musical education, but also for personal development and ensuring the stability of the social environment in general. For this, music educators need to approach the full and effective use of the possibilities of percussion instruments, recognizing them not only as a means of performance, but also as a means with educational and psychological influence.

Conclusion.

Percussion instruments, as an important means of musical education, are of great importance not only in forming the aesthetic taste of students, but also in managing their emotional state and instilling a positive mood. Scientific and practical analysis shows that training with percussion instruments increases a person's sensitivity to rhythm, reduces stress, develops teamwork, activity and emotional harmony. This article comprehensively covers the musical possibilities, psychological and pedagogical effects of percussion instruments, as well as the mechanisms for their use in the educational process. Based on the analyzed literature and practical experience, it can be said that these types of instruments serve as an effective musical tool for forming a positive emotional state. In the future, it is necessary to widely and purposefully use percussion instruments in musical and pedagogical activities, and to study their educational, social and psychological potential in more depth. At the same time, the development of special methodological recommendations and curricula for the use of percussion instruments in the music education system remains an urgent issue.

List of used literature:

1. Askarova Z. The role of national instruments in children's music education // Art and culture. – 2020. – No. 1. – P. 22–26.
2. Anokhina P. I. Musical psychology and emotions. – Moscow: Music, 2003.
3. Gault, B. M. Music Learning through Movement: Exploring the Fundamentals. – New York: Routledge, 2015.
4. Ismoilova G. Emotional environment in music and pedagogical activity. –

Tashkent: Science, 2022.

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5. Solov'ev A. N. Music and human psyche. – St. Petersburg: Composer, 2004.

6. Kurbonov M. Theoretical and practical foundations of music education. -
Tashkent: Teacher, 2019.

7. Zimnyaya I. A. Psychology education. - Moscow: Logos, 2001.